

PSYCHOLOGISM IN THE IMAGE OF A WOMAN IN THE WORKS OF GUY DE MAUPASSANT AND ABDULLA QAHHOR

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933883>

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Abstract:

the novels and stories of the outstanding writers of French and Uzbek literature - Guy de Maupassant and Abdullah Qahhor have originality and closeness in depicting the ideal of a woman. In particular, both creators often pay attention to a deep analysis of the inner world and psyche of the characters in order to ensure a competent conclusion of their works. They are trying to explore their spiritual world.

Key words:

plot, compositional construction, psyche, psychologism, typology, paradigmatic relations, portrait, gesture, facial expressions, hilvat, pamphlet, detail, grocer, midwife.

Introduction

In world literary studies, attention to clarifying the relationship between Eastern and Western literature has always been a priority. Basing the literary-aesthetic experiences achieved in both of them on the example of stylistic closeness in the choice of images and artistic representation of the creators is important in terms of enriching the theoretical views related to mutual literary influence. It is worth noting that the novels and stories of prominent writers of French and Uzbek literature - Guy de Maupassant and Abdulla Qahhor - are similar in describing the ideal of a woman. Proving their methodological closeness in interpreting and depicting the image of a woman makes it possible to define the paradigmatic relations formed under literary influence.

Literature review

The image of a woman in the literature of all nations bases its poetic interpretation in accordance with the national outlook, region, and culture. As a result, it is proved that the image of a woman is one of the traditional images in literature, and the poetics of her description is developing. When the great French writer Guy de Maupassant stepped on the threshold of creativity, he was faced

with a literary heritage of three generations - critical realism of Stendhal, Balzac and Flaubert, V. Hugo, J. Sand and G. de Maupassant's romanticism and naturalism, led by E. Zolya and the Goncourt brothers. That is why critics who later studied Maupassant's work said that the traditions of all three schools can be seen in his works.⁵⁶

In the development of Uzbek literature, in particular, in the growth and development of the realistic story, which is considered a new genre, the service of the great word artist Abdulla Qahhor was great. In the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, when Uzbek literature was undergoing a renewal process, A. Qahhor contributed to the development of storytelling, which is considered a sub-genre of the epic genre, just as Abdulla Kodiri reformed Uzbek novels, Khamza Hakim-zoda reformed dramaturgy, and Cholpon shepiyat. Each of his works is a work of art that fascinates the reader with its artistic beauty, amazes with the maturity of its plot and composition, and excites with the perfection of its language and sincerity.

Analysis

In the field of phytoonymic designations, unmotivated analogies are noticeable, which allow us to conclude that the selected feature of the phyto-object is conditional for naming any quality of a person (for example, "pear-like" (pear) - speechless gaper; "*qovoq kalla*" - pumpkin head).

The "sexual image" of a woman in Turkish is most vividly reflected through zoolexics. At the same time, it is noteworthy that female zoonyms are described in more detail than phytolexics. Thus, metaphorical words are common among zoonyms, the prototypes of which are the physiological characteristics of the sexual structure. In the category of women, love and eroticism are represented, as well as animals. A sexually attractive woman corresponds to the zoonyms "swan", "canary", "attractive girl"; chicken, also chicken, spring chicken "chicken, chick", "attractive girl", quail "ordinary quail" slang, "attractive woman, girl", pigeon "pigeon" slang, "attractive girl or woman".

The attractive image of a woman can be given by the metaphor of "like a snake". In Turkish folk aphorisms, the simile "Let there be a snake in every house" is used. It is logical that a woman is likened to a snake with her wit, magic ability, smartness and resourcefulness, as well as a deadly poison.

In order to express the image of a woman by means of phytonyms, such as "*rayhon hidli*", "*gul kabi*", "*like flower*", similes can be used. Examples of phytonyms used in a negative sense are "tick-tongued", (poisonous tongue), "garlic-like",

⁵⁶ Guy de Maupassant's life and work are detailed in the following sources: Yu.I.Danilin. Mopassan. Life and creation. M; 1968. History of French literature. M; Izd-vo AN SSSR, 1959, volume III, p. 191-233.

(sticky, restless). In Turkish, the phytonym "*kabak çiçeği gibi*" is widely used to refer to colorful and cheerful women.

Guy de Maupassant was one of the naturalist writers. In his novel "Azizim" ("Bel Ami"), the moral depravity of an aristocratic person and the misdeeds of a representative of the bourgeoisie are revealed. Naturalism is derived from the Latin word "natura" - "nature", through which changes in social life are considered to depend on the laws of nature. In the depiction of events and events, importance is attached to accurately portraying vital material. Emphasis is placed on human biological and physiological needs. It is observed that in the novel "Azizim" attention is paid to revealing the character of the main character in this aspect. The hero of this novel, which brought great fame to the writer, is George Du Rois, the son of a Norman peasant - Azizim learned to steal and cheat from big financial tycoons, political dragons, mastered it, and soon became a farang extortionist. Nicknamed "Azizim", this ex-non-commissioned officer is handsome, strong, with a mustache and a hawk nose that women dream of, so he begins his career by hunting rich women. At first, his friend hangs Forest'e's wife. It uses a woman's journalistic skills. After Foreste dies, he marries the widow Madeleine. All the property left by Foreste will go to his account.

Madeleine uses all her skills and writes articles for her new husband. Durois, who soon became a well-known journalist, was appointed the head of the chronicle department of the newspaper. With this, Durois takes the coveted first step in society. Then he declares his love for the wife of Mr. Walter, the editor-in-chief of the newspaper. After easily trapping him with tricks, he participates in the parties held in the most prestigious houses in Paris through him. Now he wants his wife to be from a cyborg family. For this purpose, Durois lures Suzanne, the owner's daughter of Mr. Walter, into a love affair. In the meantime, it becomes known that Madeleine is having an affair with deputy and minister Larosh-Mate. Durois, having captured the minister and his wife in a secret apartment under the testimony of the police commissioner, easily divorces Madeleine, and for her unfaithfulness to her husband, Madeleine is also deprived of her inheritance. Thus, Durois marries the beautiful Suzanne, who has a dowry of a million. As his father-in-law, Mr. Walter, pointed out, now all the ways were open to him: he could become a deputy, a minister, even the mayor of France. Therefore, George Durois is recognized as a necessary and honorable person who has adapted to all the rules of the bourgeois system.

Writer used his pamphlet "Male Prostitute" as the subject of the novel. But here the word "prostitute" is used in the sense of "traitor" and not in the sense of pervert.

It is said that Maupassant was an extreme womanizer. Taking this into account, Tolstoy remembers that she knew that "the meaning of life is in women and love..." In fact, this mentality is deeply embedded in the content of Maupassant's novel "Life". Also, his works such as "Savatsoch" and "Ms. Erme" began with the words "I am fascinated by the mentally retarded" and covered the theme of madness, mental depression and related diseases.

In the writer's stories from the collection of short stories called "Tele court", the corrupt life in the bourgeois society, the physiognomy of men and women given a sensual feeling are created in a humorous way. They are people who live in the dream of only one goal: pleasure, and are deprived of human feelings such as working, building a family and having children.

All creators often pay attention to the deep analysis of the inner world of the characters in order to ensure an educated output of their works. They try to explore their spiritual world. Often, the writer does not use too many words, but relies more on details, uses a portrait, human actions, gestures and facial expressions.

When talking about Abdulla Qahhor's work and his unique methodology, it should be emphasized that he is a master psychologist. The writer knows all the secrets of his characters. Nothing escapes his attention. A. Qahhor deeply feels his heart, his changing appearance and knows how to clearly show it. In the creative style of A. Qahhor, the issue of speech is of great importance.

A. Qahhor's works contain a lot of images of women with negative characteristics. Among them, the image of Munishkhan in the novel "Sarob" is immediately noticeable. She grew up as a selfish daughter of a wealthy family. Therefore, he despises others and puts himself above everyone. This disease of selfishness never allowed him to love anyone else. Benihoya, the beautiful Munish Khan, takes her own life due to her low character. He thinks more about capturing the male race. He fell into the path of depravity and died a tragic death. A charming, modern, patriotic girl like Munishkhan, who fascinates people not only with her external beauty, but also with her intelligence, taste, and inner grace, commits suicide and shoots herself with a pistol. Neither Saidi nor others know what he got himself into. The reason for this was that Munishkhan could not get used to living without love and unhappiness. This was revealed in the letter he wrote before his death: "The world is full of happiness, only I was unhappy."

Norkozi's wife in A.Qahhor's story "Mayiz yemagan xotin" or "Xo'rozqand" bride in "To'yda aza" story, due to her lightness, also ranks among the Venuses in Munishkhan and "Nurli Cho'qqilar".

The image of Turgunoy in "Maston" is contrary to the enthusiastic and fearless Maston, who is very empty, simple, and fearless. He lacks the courage to fight for his own happiness.

A.Qahhor himself writes about the role of the artist's responsibility in revealing human psychology: "Psychology gave us an opportunity to think seriously about paying attention to the inner world of people, their subtle aspects and beauty.

This is the most important aspect of writing skills. A.Qahhor, who strictly adhered to what he said, tried to reveal his inner world convincingly and fully, while impartially touching the human character in almost every work. For example, in his story "Asror Bobo", a mother whose son went to war always remembers her son. His strength is limited to crying. It sits restlessly both on the stove and on the table. Artistic psychology reveals the psyche of the character, his behavior serves to justify his actions and words psychologically. The writer directly or indirectly describes the psyche of the character is possible.

The "inner monologue" of the character's thoughts and feelings, consciousness "in the style of the stream", or from the author's language (the author's speech that is not his own) description is a direct form of psychological image.⁵⁷

As Ibrahim Haqqul said: "Every word, every phrase in the stories and stories of Abdullah Qahhor is so stable and strong that it is almost impossible to change them with another word, phrase or sentence." Abdulla Qahhor's attitude to words, the art of using words is known to many people: he is greedy for words. He chooses the word too much and uses it too much. Most of the works inherited from him are of special importance because they are made of words with blood running in their veins, eyes, ears, and consciousness open."⁵⁸

Discussion

Guy de Maupassant's story "Darbadar", although a poor carpenter named Randel goes out in search of bread in order not to support his sisters, and is chased by a gendarme, the image of him seeing a girl - someone's servant in the distance and raping her out of excitement - deserves special attention. pulls The writer notes that Randel's mental state was "like a dog at a quail." The girl, unaware of this, was carrying two full buckets of milk on her way to the village. Randel leans down and

⁵⁷ Kuronov D. Introduction to literary studies. - Tashkent: Akademnashr, 2006. - 56.

⁵⁸ The bravery of Ibrahim Haqqul Abdullah Qahhor. Essay. - "Tafakkur", 2007. - p.11.

watches the girl. The girl raised her head to look at him, laughed and said: "Was it you who was talking about song?" - he asks.

This speech of the girl shows the simplicity and sincerity of her character, politeness and decency. But the young man does not listen to the girl's words, angrily grabs the girl by the shoulders and silently knocks her down the road. The girl starts to scream when the bucket in her hand falls to the ground and the milk spills out, but Khilvat, knowing that it is useless to call someone for help in a deserted place and that the guy is not going to kill her anymore, does not say anything, she does not resist, she does not get angry, because although this guy is very rude - at, his strength is favorable to him. However, when the girl regains consciousness and gets up, she remembers the spilled milk, gets very angry, takes off her shoes and throws them at the boy, if he doesn't pay for the milk, she wants to hit him on the head.

In this place, the writer intended to refer to many things through the "spilled milk" detail - the loss of honor, pride, and sustenance. The guy in high spirits can't understand the reason for the girl's anger, but when the mood dissipates a little, he rushes and runs away from what he has done. If it was a girl, she would chase after him and throw stones, and some of the stones would hit the boy's back.

Such pictures mean that women and men become weak in front of lust and then regret. In the story "Rosalie Prudan" by Guy de Maupassan, it is stated that the white daughter of the Warambo gentlemen from Manta, named Rosalie Prudan, hid her double life from her masters, killed the child born in her room at night without telling anyone, buried it in the garden, and then the secret was revealed and she was tried, but the court acquitted her.

If it weren't for an incredible situation, it would have been like an ordinary incident that all lame girls do, says the writer.

Prudan sewed and prepared a lot of things for the boy with his own hands, he sewed these things at night for three months, and he carried a candle with him to sew these things at night. Rosalie again went to the same husband midwife for advice, and the midwife went to her and explained what to do if she suddenly went into labor and did not have time to call someone for help, and she also found a house for the girl in Poissy. The grocer and the midwife testify to this. Based on this, everyone feels that the girl did not want to kill her child. Rosalie admits that she did this horrible thing because she knew well that the Warambos eat haraam and if they find out about it, they will throw her out, and she cannot support her children because they are twins.

A couple of Warambos, one of the prominent people of the village, were sitting in the hall, angry that a disgraceful woman had dared to defame their house. They were so quick to send the girl to the guillotine that very moment, before they even tried her, that even the smallest evidence came out of their mouths like a sentence.

The woman on trial was beautiful, tall, more urbane than the women of her class, a low-Normandian, and sat silent with tears in her eyes. This characteristic indicates that a woman has a psychological character. Many believe that she did this barbaric act out of anger, because everything she did showed that she was hoping to raise her first child.

The girl was hiding the boy's father with all her heart. He was the nephew of Mr. Warambo. The girl tells that he flattered and deceived her on the day of God, and that she indulged in it, especially after he told her that you are beautiful, cute, and I like you very much. After all, I am alone, an orphan, I am a loser. I have no one in the bright world, no one to talk to, and no one to tell my sorrows to.

I have no parents, no sisters, no brothers. From the first time he spoke to me, it was like a long-lost brother. So, one evening, he went to the river bank, said that we will sit there, where no one will disturb... I went... After that, I don't know, I don't know either... He hugged me, I didn't hug him... no... do you believe, it didn't happen after all. ...I became pregnant, I found out only after a month...

As soon as the girl found out that she was pregnant, she couldn't control herself and cried bitterly. The midwife went to Budenkhanim and told her that she had to collect more money.

In the work, the psychology of the character is reflected in his actions. The character's words, facial expressions (mimicry), physiological the revelation of the psyche is indirect by showing the changes is a psychological image. These two forms of mental imagery are mutually exclusive fills, therefore, the writer in describing the psyche of a certain character it makes good use of both of these.⁵⁹

Conlcusion

The above speech expression shows his three signs in the psychological image of the hero. The first sign is that he is very desperate and helpless. The second sign is that he lives involuntarily in a big and scary house. The third sign is that he is not cruel and murderous.

⁵⁹ Muhammedova H.E. Typology of the Female Character in the Works of Charles Dickens: Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation in Philology. - Tashkent, 2019. -p.15.

Rosalie Prudence's three-character lifestyle is also distinguished by the fact that it does not resemble the life of ordinary heroes. Therefore, the author uses the image of the psyche to show this female character.

Rosalie Prue told the court: "Got earlier than I expected, had a seizure. When I finished washing the dishes in the kitchen, the pain started. I do not know how long I struggled! It may have been an hour, two hours, maybe even three hours; I lost consciousness because of the pain. Then I was as strong as I could, and the boy fell to the ground. Ugh, honestly, I am so happy. I took it from the ground and did everything my Budenkhan told me. I do not remember any of them. Now, as soon as I lay down on the bed, the pain started again, it hurt so much that the world became dark in my eyes! If you could see this, you would never dream of a child! Labor began again. For another hour or two, there is no one with me. Can the second one be born? The second child... look at this, two... true... true... two... I took him from the ground, just like the first one, and laid him down next to the previous one... You tell me if it will be like that! Twins! If I get twenty francs a month. Think for yourself! Even if it was a bit, it was worth it... if not me... two! My head is stuck... Tell me what can I do? Could I just take one out and... do that? How do I know! I said yes, I am dead now... I threw a pillow on them in agony... after I could not feed them both... I threw myself on top of them: I cried and threw up until dawn. In the meantime, of course, both of them died under the pillow. After that, I went down to the garden with the corpses of both of them, found the gardener's spade, and dug two holes in two places. I buried both of them in two places so that they would not talk about their mothers again. Who knows if the children who have not seen the world will talk about their mother or not. After that, I returned home and went to bed. I was so sick that I could not get up. They called a doctor; he knew everything as soon as he saw it.

Some of the judges were blowing their noses to stop the tears coming to their eyes, and the women in the hall were sobbing. When the girl tells the place where she buried her children, a heart-wrenching wail erupts from her chest.

Women's talkativeness, ugly and unattractive appearance, inappropriate dressing also show them as a negative character type.

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